

M11: Provision of a methodology for detection of predictors for extreme events

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Introduction

- High-resolution (km-scale) climate models (convection permitting models; CPMs) simulate heavy precipitation, urban heatwaves, and other variables considerably more realistically than their coarser counterparts
- However, km-scale models require huge computational resources, thus preventing the generation of large ensembles of climate projections
- Event-based dynamical downscaling (EBD) reduces the required computational resources by focusing on specific events of interest, enabling the generation of large ensembles of specific events
- EBD requires detection of events of interest from a parent model, typically from a global climate model (GCM) with coarse horizontal resolution, which cannot reproduce such events
- The focus is on the detection of heatwaves and heavy precipitation events, as km-scale models offer greatest added value for such events

Introduction

Different approaches have been examined for detecting potential heatwave and heavy precipitation events on different domains

- Detection of heatwaves over Emilia-Romagna domain
- Different statistical methods for detecting Emilia-Romagna heavy precipitation events
- Detection based on statistical models for Nordic domains
- Detection based on machine learning for Nordic domains

Main questions

- How well can observed heatwaves be detected from a GCM?
- How well can heavy precipitation events that occurred in CPM or observations be detected from a parent GCM or global reanalysis? How can the detection skill be optimized.
- Given the typical usage of regional climate models (RCMs) as intermediate models between GCMs and CPMs, can RCMs be used as a filter to improve the optimization of the detection skill?
- Are the detection methods developed in the historical climate applicable in future climate with comparable skill?
- Are the detection methods developed on a single domain applicable to different domain sizes?

1 Detection of heatwaves in Emilia-Romagna

Heatwave Detection : Using 90p tasmax in JJA as an index

Bias Correction & Region Selection

- **Model Bias:** EC-Earth exhibits a warm bias over the Emilia-Romagna (ER) relative to ERG5 observations, likely due to coarse topography.
- **Impact:** Uncorrected bias directly skews heatwave event detection.
- **Solution:** Analysis restricted to the **ER Plain** (Lat: 44.6°–45.1°N, Lon: 10.5°–12.8°E).
- **Result:** Improved alignment of daily Tmax "hot tails" (>35°C) between EC-Earth and ERA5.

Map of 90p tasmax in JJA

PDF of Daily Tmax during JJA (Model vs Observation)

PDF of Daily Tmax during JJA (Model vs Observation)

Heatwave Detection : Model-Obs Evaluation

- Models (EC-Earth, SLENS) daily tasmax show good agreement with observations for temperatures around 32C.
- **Extreme Tails:** Both EC-Earth and SLENS overestimate the frequency and intensity of daily tasmax over 35C.
- **Warm Bias:** Discrepancy emerges at the **85th percentile** and above (Q-Q analysis), with a warm bias of approximately **1–2C**.
- **Conclusion:** Despite over-amplifying heat extremes, the bias remains within a manageable range, providing confidence for heatwave event detection.

2 Detection of heavy precipitation events in Emilia-Romagna

Data & domain

- Eraclito61 observations
 - 1961 – 2024
 - Daily precipitation
 - Spatial grid ~5 km spacing
- ERA5 reanalysis
 - Same period
 - Daily precipitation and 6-h 850 hPa geopotential
 - Spatial grid 0.25 degrees

- Only transition seasons (Apr, May, Jun, Sep, Oct, Nov)
- Dates are sorted according to daily spatial mean precipitation separately for observations and for ERA5
- Find how many strongest ERA5 events contain n strongest observed precipitation events (n = 15, 21, 32, 64)
- Additional criterion: Circulation type classification using ERA5 850 hPa geopotential
 - Each day has 4 CTs
- Skill: sensitivity parameter (low FALSE ALARM and MISS; high HIT)

$$\text{sensitivity} = \text{hit_ratio} - \text{false_alarm_ratio} = \frac{\text{hit}}{\text{hit} + \text{miss}} - \frac{\text{false_alarm}}{\text{false_alarm} + \text{hit}}$$

Circulation types

Example: strongest observed event

18 September 2024

Figure 1.1 Date: 2024-9-18; Total daily precipitation in region: 92.23 mm

Figure 1.2 Date: 2024-9-18; Total daily precipitation in region: 23.1 mm

Circulation types: 9, 3, 3, 3

CTC: 9, occurrence: 4%, time: 2024-09-18 00:00:00

CTC: 3, occurrence: 11%, time: 2024-09-18 06:00:00

CTC: 3, occurrence: 11%, time: 2024-09-18 12:00:00

CTC: 3, occurrence: 11%, time: 2024-09-18 18:00:00

- 1st (strongest) event in Eraclito61 sorted days
- 151st event in ERA5 sorted days!!!

- So, 151 strongest events from ERA5 should be downscaled to ensure that the strongest observed event is captured
- Similarly, to capture n strongest observed events, the following numbers of strongest ERA5 events (N_{ERA5}) are needed:
 - $n = 15, N_{\text{ERA5}} = 191$
 - $n = 21, N_{\text{ERA5}} = 191$
 - $n = 32, N_{\text{ERA5}} = 344$
 - $n = 64, N_{\text{ERA5}} = 986$
- Therefore, ERA5 precipitation cannot be used alone for detection of potential heavy precipitation events
- Use circulation types

Example: 15 strongest observed events (R > 55 mm)

Date / Obs. precip [mm] / ERA5 precip [mm] / CT_00h / CT_06h / CT_12h / CT_18h

2024-09-18 / 92.23 / 23.10 / 6 / 6 / 6 / 6
 1966-11-04 / 84.47 / 54.83 / 6 / 6 / 10 / 10
 2023-05-16 / 75.35 / 31.00 / 9 / 9 / 9 / 9
 1995-06-24 / 70.08 / 40.65 / 9 / 9 / 9 / 9
 1996-10-08 / 68.06 / 24.64 / 6 / 6 / 9 / 9
 2005-04-11 / 65.84 / 27.25 / 9 / 9 / 9 / 9
 1994-06-12 / 65.84 / 28.62 / 9 / 9 / 9 / 9
 2023-05-02 / 64.14 / 28.18 / 9 / 9 / 9 / 9
 1981-06-23 / 62.02 / 24.28 / 9 / 9 / 9 / 9
 1973-09-26 / 61.12 / 40.79 / 6 / 6 / 9 / 9
 1963-09-08 / 61.04 / 22.18 / 9 / 9 / 9 / 9
 1989-09-03 / 60.40 / 36.34 / 5 / 5 / 5 / 5
 2005-09-18 / 58.67 / 35.87 / 9 / 9 / 9 / 9
 2024-10-19 / 57.93 / 33.74 / 6 / 6 / 6 / 6
 2006-09-17 / 57.78 / 36.83 / 6 / 10 / 10 / 10

Histogram of CT occurrence from n = 15 EraclitoSorted data

Contingency for the 15 strongest observed events

m = 15 EraclitoSorted; n = 191 ERASorted; HIT = 13; MISS = 2; FALSE_ALARM = 33; REJECTION = 143; SENSITIVITY = 0.6792

- Using only ERA5 precipitation, 191 events are needed to capture the 15 strongest observed events
- With circulation types, 36 events are needed to capture 13 out of 15 strongest observed events

3 Detection of heavy precipitation events based on statistical models

Simulations

- Obtained from the NorCP experiment
- Two time periods (training and validation):
 - 1986 – 2005
 - 2081 – 2100
- Models: EC-Earth (GCM) – HCLIM38-ALADIN (RCM 12 km) – HCLIM38-AROME (CPM 3 km)
- Domains: NorCP (grey), South Sweden (green), Norrköping (blue), Malmö (red)

Validation methods

- HIT RATE = $TP / (TP + FP)$
- FALSE ALARM RATE = $FP / (FP + FN)$
- MATTHEWS CORRELATION COEFFICIENT (MCC)

$$MCC = \frac{TP \times TN - FP \times FN}{\sqrt{(TP + FP)(TP + FN)(TN + FP)(TN + FN)}}$$

ECE	AROME	
	yes	no
yes	TP	TN
no	FP	FN

Results

- Historical data
- NorCP domain
- Always compare to precipitation in AROME (the "truth", i.e. the predictand)
- First use only daily convective precipitation from EC-Earth as the predictor:

HIT RATE	FA RATE	MCC
0,424	0,064	0,392

- Next: improve the scores
- Use "ingredients for convection"
- Multiple linear regression and logistic regression
- Updated predictors in GCM (daily data): convective precipitation, K Index (75 percentile), Lifted index (25 percentile), CAPE (75 percentile), moisture convergence on 850 hPa (75 percentile), wind shear 1000 – 500 (75 percentile)

	HIT RATE	FA RATE	MCC
Original method	0,424	0,064	0,392
Linear regression	0,516	0,050	0,462
Logistic regression	0,402	0,066	0,336

Results

Does linear regression give different results on a smaller subdomain (next slide) and in another period (later) if we use the same predictors and coefficients?

	DOMAIN	HIT RATE	FA RATE	MCC
Original method	NorCP	0,424	0,064	0,360
	South Sweden	0,353	0,072	0,281
	Malmo	0,337	0,074	0,263
	Norrköping	0,353	0,071	0,281
Linear regression	NorCP	0,516	0,054	0,463
	South Sweden	0,402	0,066	0,336
	Malmo	0,402	0,066	0,336
	Norrköping	0,386	0,068	0,318
Logistic regression	NorCP	0,402	0,066	0,336
	South Sweden	0,402	0,066	0,336
	Malmo	0,435	0,063	0,372
	Norrköping	0,353	0,072	0,281

Skill decrease on smaller domains

Skill increase with regression

Smaller domains

Spatial shift of precipitation

Solution: use RCM as a filter between GCM and CPM to remove non-extreme events

	DOMAIN	HIT RATE	FA RATE	MCC
Original method	NorCP	0,424	0,064	0,360
	South Sweden	0,353	0,072	0,281
	Malmo	0,337	0,074	0,263
	Norrköping	0,353	0,071	0,281
ALADIN included	NorCP	0,609	0,043	0,565
	South Sweden	0,478	0,058	0,420
	Malmo	0,538	0,051	0,487
	Norrköping	0,533	0,052	0,425
Linear regression – – ALADIN included	NorCP	0,652	0,043	0,613
	South Sweden	0,527	0,053	0,475
	Malmo	0,576	0,047	0,528
	Norrköping	0,538	0,513	0,487

Skill decrease on smaller domains

Large skill increase with RCM (ALADIN)

Highest skill with RCM & regression

4 Detection of heavy precipitation events based on machine learning

ML model configuration

- CNN (better compared to our U-Net)
- Input layer -> 5 hidden layers -> upscale resolution
- BCEWithLogitsLoss
- Adam

- Pairs of EC-Earth outputs as predictors and ALADIN extreme precipitation mask as ground-truth (from NorCP)
- 99th percentile of daily maximum of 1h precipitation output is used for generating the mask of extremes
- 1986 – 2003 training period
- 2004 – 2005 validation period
- Variables used
 - pr, prc, psl
 - ua, va, ta, zg, hus
 - Pressure levels (hPa): 1000, 850, 700, 500, 250, 100
 - CAPE, CIN, K-index, Lifted index, shear, moisture flux convergence, IVTmag
 - Daily frequency

GCM outputs, inputs to the ML model; see above for the list of variables used. Here shown precipitation flux, temperature on 1000 hPa and geopotential height on 850 hPa for winter (upper panel) and summer (lower panel).

Probability of extreme precipitation obtained from the ML model; for winter (upper panel) and summer (lower panel)

Mask of extreme precipitation from HCLIM12 maximum daily precipitation for winter (upper panel) and summer (lower panel).

Validation methodology

- Fractions Skill Score (FSS; e. g. Mittermaier, 2021)
 - Perfect score FSS=1
 - The worst score FSS=0
- Window size is 30 grid points
- Threshold for extremes is probability of extreme event > 0.5

Examples

- Examples of different detection skills in the following 3 slides
- Left panels: probability of detection of extreme precipitation based on GCM data
- Right panels: mask of extreme precipitation in RCM

FSS = 0.21

FSS = 0.81

FSS = 0.01

Validation

- Overall FSS = 0.24
- Other measures:

Evaluation of the ML model detection for the whole year for the period 2004 – 2005. From left to right: accuracy, probability of false detection, precision and recall.

Conclusions

- Detection of heatwaves from GCMs is feasible after bias correction
- Detecting potential extreme precipitation events from large scale data (GCM or reanalysis) is a demanding task
- Using circulation types can considerably improve detection skill, particularly for limited area domains
- Using instability indices from GCM helps in making decisions about days with extreme precipitation in CPM
- Linear and logistic regression improve the detection skill
- Incorporating RCM (with a suitable number of runs) contributes to further improvement – benefits outweigh costs
- ML has very good performance during winter, but struggles with stochastic summer convection

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